

Sustainable Alternatives to Mitigate Stubble Burning in Northern India: A Comprehensive Analysis

Abstract

Stubble burning is the practice of removing agricultural waste from the field by setting on fire the straw stubble that is left on the land after harvesting grains like paddy, wheat, etc in order to prepare it for the next round of seeding. It has become a common practice in India to remove agricultural waste from fields after harvesting grains. This study aims to understand the environmental and health impacts of stubble burning, including its contribution to air pollution, climate change, and soil degradation. The study then discusses the challenges and opportunities for reducing the use of stubble burning, such as the development of alternative methods for crop residue management. It further goes on to list some potential economic and social benefits of reducing stubble burning, such as improved air quality, reduced greenhouse gas emissions, and increased soil health. This study is important because stubble burning is a major environmental and health problem in India. This study will provide valuable information about the impacts of stubble burning and the potential for reducing its use. This information can be used to develop policies and programs to address this problem and improve the environment and health of the people of India.

Keywords: Stubble Burning, Rice straw, environment, health impacts, alternatives

1. Understanding the Cause

The rationales behind stubble burning are intricate and diverse. The rice-wheat cropping system faces limitations due to the narrow time frame between rice harvest and wheat planting. A fully automated combine harvester, coupled with a thresher, is deployed to efficiently harvest the crop and gather the grains in a single operation through multiple stages. This practice exacerbates the issue, leaving around 20–30 cm of stubble on the ground after rice harvest, impeding subsequent crop sowing for farmers. Any delay in wheat planting could detrimentally impact the crop, necessitating the removal or utilization of residual rice straw. Furthermore, in the context of the current intensive agricultural model, upholding the pace of farming activities through manual labor or livestock becomes challenging.

The time window allotted to farmers for planting the succeeding wheat crop is only 7–10 days, extending to 15–20 days for basmati and traditional high-yielding rice, respectively (Sahai et al., 2011). In the northwestern regions of India, paddy straw is not favored as livestock feed due to its elevated silica content, standing at 8% on a dry matter basis (Singh et al., 1996). Rice straw demonstrates inadequacy in mineral and protein content while being high in lignocellulose and fiber composition.

Although burning presents a seemingly straightforward approach to managing various pests, it remains ensnared in numerous controversies. The act of field incineration has demonstrated instances of favorable pathogen load control. Some farmers contend that this method enhances soil productivity by reducing weed and pathogen burdens (Lohan et al., 2018). The unwieldy and voluminous nature of rice residue necessitates challenging storage requirements. Incineration of paddy straw eliminates residual material from the field, simplifying subsequent tractor operations and conserving fuel for subsequent crop sowing.

The decomposition process of rice residue within the soil is protracted, attributed to its diminished N-content and elevated C:N ratio, compounded by insufficient post-harvest soil moisture (Goswami et al., 2020). Remarkably, a mere fraction of farmers—less than one percent—choose to incorporate rice straw due to the heightened tillage demands associated with this approach compared to burning (Department of Agriculture, Punjab, 2005). For many farmers, the simplest and most cost-effective strategy for rice stubble disposal remains burning.

2. Extent of Occurrence

India stands as the world's second-largest crop producer, according to the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations. The generation of total crop residue (dry matter) has shown an upward trajectory, escalating from 80 MT in 1950–1951 to 520 MT in 2017–2018 as reported by the Economic Survey of India in 2020. Among this, around 100 MT is subjected to burning. The practice of burning crop residues in situ exhibits notable disparities based on crop type and geographic region. For example, the proportion of rice crop residues subjected to in situ burning ranges from 8% to 80% across various Indian states. Similar variations apply to wheat crop residues (10–23%), sugarcane (25%), and other crops (10%). Notably, approximately 11.3 MT of paddy straw is annually burned, with Haryana and Punjab accounting for 16.9% and 49.47%, respectively (MoA and FW, 2019).

The findings of Sidhu and Beri (2005) indicate that Punjab witnessed a total paddy stubble production of 18.8 million tonnes in 2004–2005, of which 15 million tonnes were openly burned in fields. Their study further reveals that a substantial 80% of rice harvested via combine harvesters is subjected to field burning. According to Singh et al. (2008), Punjab generates roughly 17 million tonnes of rice straw annually, with a staggering 90% being burnt openly in fields.

3. Consequences associated with it

The incineration of agricultural residues engenders substantial land and water pollution at local and regional scales. The combustion of paddy straw, for instance, leads to considerable nutrient depletion, comprising 3.85 million tonnes of organic carbon, 59,000 tonnes of nitrogen, 20,000 tonnes of phosphorus, and 34,000 tonnes of potassium (Kumar and Joshi, 2013). This disturbance significantly disrupts the soil's nutrient balance. The process of burning results in the complete combustion and atmospheric loss of straw carbon, nitrogen, and sulfur. According to Singh et al. (2008), the burning of rice residues in Punjab during 2001–2002 incurred nutrient losses of 2,400 kg of C, 35 kg of N, 3.2 kg of P, 21 kg of K, and 2.7 kg of S per hectare. Although carbon and nitrogen losses were nearly total, phosphorus, potassium, and sulfur losses were partial, ranging from approximately 20% to 60%.

The combustion of agricultural residues gives rise to smoke emissions which, when combined with existing air gases like methane, nitrogen oxide, and ammonia, can lead to severe atmospheric pollution. According to Gupta et al.'s (2004) study, burning one tonne of straw releases 3 kg of particulate matter, 60 kg of CO (equivalent to 94.2 kg CO₂), 1,460 kg of CO₂, 4.5 kg of CH₄ (equivalent to 47.1 kg CO₂), 2 kg of SO₂ (equivalent to 0.88 kg CO₂), and 0.07 kg of N₂O (equivalent to 47 kg CO₂), summing up to approximately 1647 kg CO₂ equivalent, along with 199 kg of ash. These gaseous emissions and carbonaceous aerosols possess a pivotal role in atmospheric chemistry, impacting both the regional environment and its connections to global climate change.

Moreover, these emissions pose health risks, exacerbating conditions such as asthma, chronic bronchitis, and reduced lung function. From 2003 to 2019, agricultural residue burning contributed to 44,000–98,000 premature deaths annually due to particulate matter exposure-related causes (Lan et al., 2022). Additionally, the incineration of crop residues indirectly contributes to elevated ozone pollution levels.

The repercussions extend to soil quality, as the incineration of crop residue leads to detrimental outcomes. The combustion process results in the destruction of existing soil minerals, detrimentally affecting the subsequent crop cultivation. In their investigation, Gupta et al. (2004) approximated that straw burning escalates soil temperatures to a range of 33.8–42.2°C at a depth of 1 cm. Nitrogen loss is substantial, ranging from 23% to 73%, and there's an immediate decline in fungal and bacterial populations at a depth of 2.5 cm. According to a study by the Department of Soils at PAU in 2006, Punjab generates approximately 23 million tonnes of rice straw and 17 million tonnes of wheat straw annually. This practice significantly elevates the soil temperature within the upper 3 inches, leading to swift alterations in the Carbon-Nitrogen equilibrium within the soil.

4. The Way Forward

i. On-site Residue Handling

Both "straw incorporation" and "straw mulching" techniques entail integrating crop residue directly into the field to enhance soil nutrient value and fertility. In the former approach, residue decomposition occurs in situ through a chemically facilitated process, while the latter involves mechanical incorporation along with seeding. The latter method holds greater utility due to its elimination of the need for separate weeding and its cost-effectiveness.

Incorporating straw into the soil yields favorable outcomes for the soil's physical, chemical, and biological attributes, including pH, organic carbon, water-holding capacity, and bulk density. Residue incorporation notably reduces soil evaporation losses by up to 50 mm and elevates moisture content by 5–10% during the winter season (Lohan et al., 2018). Over the long term, it is observed to augment the availability of zinc, copper, iron, and manganese content in the soil, while also curbing nitrate leaching. Elevated organic carbon levels foster increased bacterial and fungal populations within the soil. In a rice-wheat rotation, Beri et al. (1992) and Sidhu et al. (1995) noted that soils treated with crop residues exhibited 5–10 times more aerobic bacteria and 1.5–11 times more fungi compared to soils where residues were burned or removed. The heightened microbial population enhances the activity of soil enzymes responsible for converting unavailable nutrients into accessible forms. This practice further leads to notable reductions in irrigation and fertilizer expenses.

ii. Residue as Livestock Feed

The utilization of rice residue as animal fodder isn't widely adopted by farmers in Punjab. This hesitance primarily stems from the substantial silica content within rice residue, which creates a physical barrier hindering microbial degradation. To address this, technological advancements, particularly pre-treatment methods, offer viable solutions for sustainable straw utilization as fodder. Pre-treatment involves physical, chemical, and biological processes aimed at enhancing the palatability of livestock feed.

Physical pre-treatments encompass procedures such as grinding, water soaking, steam pressure, pelleting, and gamma irradiation. Among these, soaking is the most prevalent practice, as it enhances the softness of the lingo-cellulosic elements in straw. On the chemical front, alkaline agents like ammonia, sodium hydroxide (NaOH), lime (CaO or Ca(OH)₂), and urea are commonly employed. These alkaline substances interact with ester bonds linking lignin and cellulose or hemicellulose compounds, resulting in the softening of structural fibers and a boost in microbial activity. Cattle fed with such treated feed exhibit enhanced health and increased milk production.

iii. Residue as Cattle Bedding Material

The application of paddy straw bedding during winter has demonstrated enhancements in milk quality and quantity, attributing these benefits to improved animal comfort, health, and leg health. The utilization of paddy straw bedding serves to keep animals warm and regulate heat loss rates from their bodies, contributing to their overall well-being. Additionally, this practice offers a clean, hygienic, dry, comfortable, and non-slip environment, reducing the likelihood of injuries and lameness. Notably, the paddy straw utilized for bedding can subsequently be repurposed for biogas plants.

The implementation of paddy straw bedding has also yielded increased net profits, ranging from Rs 188 to Rs 971 per animal per month, stemming from the elevated sale of additional milk produced by cows provided with bedding (Kumar & Joshi, 2013).

iv. Residue in the Manufacturing of Paper

Rice straw stands as a viable and environmentally conscious choice for the paper and pulp sector. When combined with wheat straw in a ratio of 40:60, paddy straw holds potential for paper manufacturing. Established chemical techniques exist to extract cellulose and phenolic compounds from straw, facilitating their utilization in paper production. Furthermore, the sludge generated within the paper industry can be harnessed for energy generation through the process of bio-methanization.

v. Production of Biogas

Utilizing rice straw for biofuel creation via anaerobic digestion presents a feasible avenue. Biogas encompasses a blend of diverse gas components, including methane (CH₄), CO₂, hydrogen sulphide (H₂S), oxygen, nitrogen, and other minor gases. However, prioritizing elevated CH₄ content remains imperative owing to its superior energy density (Ngan et al., 2020). Anaerobic digestion comprises four pivotal stages: hydrolysis, acidogenesis, acetogenesis, and methanogenesis.

vi. Preparation of Compost

Composting emerges as the most environmentally conscious approach for rice stubble management, facilitating the restoration of nutrients to the soil in readily accessible forms. Several critical aspects must be considered when crafting compost from rice straw, including:

- Substrate composition, encompassing pH, structural, biochemical, and nutritional attributes, as well as nutritive value.
- Temperature maintenance.
- Moisture content within the composting pit.
- Carbon-to-nitrogen (C:N) ratio.

Empirical investigations underscore that compost derived from rice straw can be effectively integrated into agricultural fields, leading to heightened yields alongside a simultaneous reduction in greenhouse gas emissions (IRRI, 2019).

vii. Electricity Generation

Excess rice straw, employed either individually or in conjunction with coal at power plants, emerges as a viable avenue for power generation. When subjected to combustion within a boiler or gasifier operating under low or zero oxygen conditions and high temperatures, the residues transform into producer gas (with a calorific value of 1000–1200 Kcal/Nm³) composed of CO, H, and N. This producer gas, while possessing a lower calorific value compared to liquefied petroleum gas, presents no environmental hazards (Datta et al., 2020; Yadvinder-Singh et al., 2014). Approximately 8 tonnes of paddy straw are required for a gasifier with a 1 Kilowatt-electric (kWe) capacity, on average.

The rationale for rice straw's suitability within the energy sector includes:

- Elevated calorific value (3950 Kcal per kilogram of straw versus coal's 4200 Kcal)
- Minimal ash content (18% ash compared to coal's 36%)
- Renewable, environmentally friendly, and easily accessible
- Boiler combustion efficiency nearing 100%
- Possibility of added income for farmers and millers through direct electricity sales to power plants
- Potential utility of power industry by-products like brick ash or fire ash within the cement industry
- Lower capital requirements in contrast to traditional power industries.

viii. Production of bio-Fuel

Bio-oil, a dense liquid substance, originates from organic waste materials such as bagasse, wheat residue, and rice hull via the pyrolysis process conducted at temperatures exceeding 500°C. Possessing a heating value equivalent to about 55% of diesel, bio-oil exhibits characteristics that enable its storage, pumping, and transportation akin to petroleum-derived products. This liquid can be directly burned in applications such as boilers, gas turbines, and slow and medium-speed diesel engines, serving purposes encompassing heat generation, power production, and even transportation. Additionally, it's noteworthy that bio-oil is devoid of SO₂ emissions and tends to generate low levels of NO₂.

ix. Cultivation of Mushrooms

A crucial requirement for cultivating robust mushrooms involves obtaining uncontaminated, moisture-free straw devoid of any mold presence. The paddy straw mushroom, a highly prevalent and extensively cultivated fungal species, constitutes a significant portion, approximately 50-60%, of the worldwide yield. This cultivation practice substantially enhances the economic status of farmers and presents an enduring avenue for the efficient utilization of paddy straw resources. Remarkably, a yield of 120-150 grams of paddy straw mushrooms can be obtained from every kilogram of paddy straw.

x. Residue for Household Applications

Rice byproducts have the potential for diverse applications, such as roofing thatch and household fuel. In the northern states of India, rice stubble serves as a domestic fuel source in conjunction with cow dung. In various other states, paddy straw serves a multitude of purposes including thatching material, household consumption, mulching substance, and combustible material.

5. Conclusion

It is evident that unchecked burning of agricultural residues leads to a highly destructive outcome, without question. Annually, significant financial resources from both the Central and State governments are allocated to address this persistent issue permanently. A combination of operational, socio-economic, and technical factors contributes to this detrimental situation. Despite being well aware of the adverse effects of crop residue on both living organisms and the environment, farmers find themselves in a helpless situation due to the lack of viable and economically feasible alternatives, as well as a dearth of institutional support.

The introduction of diverse benefits, both on-farm and off-farm, can revolutionize the scenario. The surplus agricultural residue holds potential for efficient utilization in the production of biofuels, biogas, biochar, electricity generation, mushroom cultivation, as well as applications in the pulp and paper board industry, and household activities. Mere imposition of stringent regulations and legal penalties, without addressing the needs of the farming community, proves ineffective. This comprehensive review encompasses various illustrative measures, policy considerations, and areas for future research exploration. The successful dissemination of these

technologies in rural areas, backed by robust government support, has the potential to alleviate the issue, particularly in the northwestern states.

A concerted endeavor involving multiple stakeholders is imperative to implement existing technologies effectively and to innovate novel solutions. Collaboration among farmers, industrial entities, agricultural researchers, extension department experts, state government officials, and all other relevant stakeholders holds paramount importance in operationalizing current technologies and devising novel strategies to collectively resolve the problem.

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